

Studies on Synthesis of Compounds Designed as CNS Depressants

S. Husain Zaheer, G. S. Sidhu, and I. K. Kacker

REGIONAL RESEARCH LABORATORY, HYDERABAD.

Drugs which depress the Central Nervous System (CNS) may affect the CNS generally or some specific centre within it. It is difficult to distinguish between the two modes of action. Also a drug may combine both types of action. Morphine-like analgesics and anti-convulsant drugs probably act on specific centres in the CNS. Hypnotics, narcotics, and general anaesthetics, on the other, depress the CNS generally. But it is seldom that a drug of this class has only a single activity and only a single mode of action. Analgesia, sedation, and hypnosis are probably only different stages of partial depression of the CNS. Drugs designed to be possibly active in one field turn out to have useful activity in an allied or even in a different field. Thus Dolantin (Pethidine), now so widely used as an analgesic, was originally designed by Eisleb as an antispasmodic.

Over the last few years, we have been engaged in the synthesis of compounds likely to be active as CNS depressants. Our work lies mainly in the field of (i) synthesis of quinazoline derivatives, (ii) synthesis of tetrahydroquinoline derivatives, and (iii) synthesis of β -phenylethylamines and tetrahydroisoquinoline derivatives.

Derivatives of Quinazoline

Seventeen new 4(3-H) quinazolones of the general formula (I) were synthesised by Kacker and Zaheer¹ by the general method of Grimmel, Guenther, and Morgan², and were screened at the K. G. Medical College, Lucknow, and the results reported by Gujral *et al.*^{3,4}

(I)

(II)

Although these compounds indicated no analgesic activity, they were found, however, to be potent hypnotics, the most potent and clinically useful compound being 2-methyl-3-*ortho*-tolyl-4(3H)-quinazolone. After animal trials, it was tested clinically on medical and surgical patients as well as on healthy volunteers and found to be a hypnotic of lesser toxicity and greater duration of activity than diallylbarbituric acid in comparable doses. This hypnotic activity in the quinazolones could possibly be explained by the presence of

the basic barbiturate skeleton in these compounds as can be seen by comparing structures (I) and (II). The ring in (I) could be considered analogous to C₄-alkyl chain at C₅ of (II).

This discovery of hypnotic activity for the first time in 4(3H)-quinazolones synthesised in this laboratory has led to a spate of work in this field at various laboratories abroad. A number of new quinazolones have now been synthesised and screened, but 2-methyl-3-*ortho*-tolyl-4(3H)-quinazolone still remains the most potent, with no adverse side effects. Ravina³ has also described its pharmacological action. The compound is now marketed by Boots Pure Drug Co. Ltd., under the name Melsedin. Laboratories Toraude, Paris, have also obtained a British Patent for its preparation (B.P. 843,073).

Work at the Strassenburgh Laboratories⁶ in U.S.A. has shown that this compound (named Tuazole by them) prolongs and potentiates the feeble analgesic activity of codeine. Gujral *et al.*⁴ have also reported anticonvulsant activity in quinazolones. The B.D.H. laboratories are also pursuing this line of work⁷.

An aspect of chemical interest is the action of the Grignard reagents on these quinazolones. This was studied by us with four quinazolones⁸ and found to lead to the fission of the heterocyclic ring with elimination of the arylamine and formation of benzoxazines. The reaction probably proceeds as follows:

Derivatives of Tetrahydroquinolines

Whereas several hundreds of compounds derived from quinoline have been synthesised and pharmacologically screened (mainly as antimalarials and amoebicides), derivatives of tetrahydroquinoline do not appear to have received the same attention. In our laboratory twenty-six new compounds of the general formula (III) have now been synthesised.⁹

That such compounds have not so far received adequate attention may be due to the lack of convenient methods of preparing the desired tetrahydroquinolines in good yields. The tetrahydroquinolines are generally obtained by high pressure hydrogenation of the corresponding quinolines. The yields are not uniformly good and hydrogenation leads to a mixture of products of varying degree of hydrogenation. The methods that we have used for preparing the tetrahydroquinolines are:

(i) *Lithium aluminium hydride reduction of appropriately substituted 3,4-dihydrocarbostyrils.*—The dihydrocarbostyrils can be prepared in good yields from *o*-nitrobenzaldehydes as described by us earlier¹⁰.

(ii) *Reduction of the corresponding quinolines by nickel-aluminium alloy in alkali solution.*—The reduction proceeds smoothly in yields of 70% and over. This is an extension of a method first described by Papa *et al.*¹¹. The tetrahydroquinolines are then condensed with freshly prepared alkylaminoalkyl chlorides. The (*N*-alkylaminoalkyl)-1,2,3,4-tetrahydroquinolines, which were obtained in good yields in this way, are now being evaluated for biological activity. One of these, in preliminary screening, has shown interesting antispasmodic and anticonvulsant activity. Its pharmacological action is in some respects reminiscent of the action of Reserpine¹².

Mayer and co-workers¹³ have cyclised *m*-substituted *N*-(γ -chloropropionyl)anilines with aluminium chloride and obtained mixtures of 5- and 7-substituted dihydrocarbostyrils, but they could not assign structures to the individual compounds. We synthesised the 7-substituted isomers unequivocally from the corresponding *o*-nitrocinnamic esters during the course of the above work and thus were able to assign structures to Mayer's compounds also.⁹

Carbostyril provides a classical example of lactam-lactim tautomerism. 3,4-Dihydrocarbostyrils can, however, exist only in the lactam form. A comparison of the U.V. and I.R. spectra of the substituted carbostyrils and corresponding 3, 4-dihydrocarbostyrils, prepared by us, has shown that the carbostyrils also exist preponderantly in the lactam form¹⁴, the carbonyl peak showing at 6.02 μ .

Isoquinoline Derivatives

Morphine contains an octahydroisoquinoline system and several isoquinoline derivatives have been synthesised for testing as analgesics and antispasmodics—till recently with negative results. We have synthesised some (*N*-alkylaminoalkyl)-1,2,3,4-tetrahydroisoquinolines (IV):

and are extending the synthesis to tetrahydroisoquinolines carrying alkyl, hydroxy, alkoxy and chlorine substituents in the benzene ring¹⁵. The compounds synthesised are being screened pharmacologically.

The tetrahydroisoquinolines needed for the above synthesis have been obtained by the Pictet-Spengler synthesis from appropriate β -phenylethylamines. β -Phenylethylamines themselves are well known to possess significant biological properties, generally sympathomimetic. We have prepared a number of β -phenylethylamines, some already known and some new, and have converted these also into dialkylaminoalkyl derivatives (V).

These compounds may be regarded as open-chain analogues of Priscooline (VI), a valuable vasodilator drug.

Preliminary results of screening indicate spasmolytic activity in these compounds.

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